

DIABETES MELLITUS AND DENTAL HEALTH: PROBLEMS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF PATIENTS IN DENTAL CLINICS

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the relationship between diabetes mellitus and dental health. The lack of knowledge of dentists and dental patients about diabetes is shown. The role of the dentist in the early diagnosis of diabetes mellitus and the features of the treatment of dental diseases in patients with diabetes are discussed.

Diabetes mellitus (DM) belongs to a group of socially significant non-communicable diseases that are widespread throughout the world. In 2012, according to various sources, there were from 347 to 371 million patients with diabetes in the world, of which 490 thousand were children. By 2030, 552 million patients with diabetes are expected (9.9% of the adult population). Patients with diabetes need life-long treatment, which is expensive and is not always fully provided by medical and social insurance systems [1-4].

In most cases (from 80 to 97%), patients develop type 2 diabetes mellitus. Type 1 diabetes (DM-1) occurs predominantly before the age of 40. More than half of the sick are children, the peak incidence is at 14 years of age. The disease begins acutely, with classic symptoms (polyuria, polydipsia, etc.; Table 1), and is usually quickly diagnosed. Type 2 diabetes (DM-2)

is mainly affected by elderly people, but every year an increasing number of people who become ill at a young and even childhood age are registered. The clinical picture of CD-2 in more than half of patients is not expressed, in many it manifests itself gradually, with non-classical or minimal symptoms (fatigue, itching, increased appetite, etc.), which do not cause concern and complaints. Therefore, CD-2 is not diagnosed for a long time, it is detected by chance. However, in 20-30% of cases, T2DM in childhood and adolescence manifests sharply, as T1DM. The danger of CD-1 and CD-2 lies in the development of chronic hyperglycemia in patients, leading to early and late vascular complications from many organs and systems of the body, the most serious are coronary heart disease (IHD), nephropathy, retinopathy, diabetic foot syndrome, polyneuropathy,

leading to disability and premature death of patients [5-8].

What a dentist should know about diabetes. Given the high prevalence of diabetes mellitus and the adverse effect on the dental health of patients, dentists should be well aware of:

Dental health in patients with diabetes is deteriorating.

There is an accelerated eruption of permanent teeth in children, more pronounced in girls; teething is accompanied by gingivitis [9].

- There are structural changes in the salivary glands, impaired salivation and biochemical changes in the composition of saliva, which in turn causes xerostomia and the development of further complications: multiple caries, candidiasis, halitosis [10, 11].

- Against the background of systemic immunosuppression, chronic diseases of the oral mucosa develop (lichen planus, recurrent aphthous stomatitis, recurrent bacterial, viral and fungal stomatitis), opportunistic infections, multiple abscesses during periodontitis, halitosis, surgical interventions, implant engraftment is worse [10, 16].

- Neurological disorders are manifested in the oral cavity in the form of stomatalgia (the main symptoms are burning in the mouth and tongue) and taste perversion; prolonged existence of stomatalgia leads to a violation of oral hygiene, and taste perversion leads to hyperphagia and obesity, inability to follow a diet; as a result, glycemic control deteriorates in diabetic patients [10].

- The composition of microflora in patients with controlled diabetes is the same as in periodontitis; in uncontrolled diabetes, it

changes: the percentage of colonies of TM7, Aqqreqatibacter, Neisseria, Gemella, Eikenella, Selenomonas, Actinomyces, Capnocytophaga, Fusobacterium, Veillonella and Streptococcus genera increases, Porphyromonas, Filifactor, Eubacterium, Synerqistetes, Tannerella and Treponema genera decreases [17].

A two-way relationship between diabetes mellitus and periodontitis has been proven.

Most patients with diabetes develop periodontal disease, in 10% of cases, patients with periodontal pathology are diagnosed with diabetes. The interaction model described by Grossi S.G. and Genco R.J. (1998) is as follows. Developing inflammatory periodontal diseases are rapidly progressing, leading to tooth loss. In turn, severe periodontal disease complicates glycemic control and increases the severity of diabetes mellitus [18].

Periodontal disease in patients with diabetes is characterized by a severe course. At the age of 12-18 years, there is a progression of gingivitis, loss of gum attachment, development of periodontitis. At the age of 15-19, 27% of adolescents have aggressive periodontitis [23, 24].

Compared with non-diabetic patients, adults with T1DM and T2DM have a more pronounced clinic of periodontal diseases: a longer duration of inflammation; 3 times more often there is a loss of attachment of the gums to the bone, the development of periodontitis; increased depth of paradontal pockets; more destruction of the alveolar bone; more lost teeth [10, 15, 20, 21, 25].

Patients with diabetes often do not have preventive habits: 90% of adolescents brush their teeth once a day, 60% do not

use flossing [26, 27], adults 40–70 years old brush their teeth once in 54% of cases, 77% do not know their HbA1 level, 42% are overweight, 32% are obese [28]. All this contributes to the worsening of both diabetes and inflammatory periodontal diseases.

Diagnostic signs and risk factors for diabetes. If we take into account the data of world statistics on the incidence of diabetes from 4.3 to 10.9% of the population [1-3], it can be assumed that every twenty-third to ninth visitor to a dental clinic has diabetes.

In addition, the identification of well-known risk factors for diabetes will help to improve the diagnosis, prevention and management of diabetes in dental patients [5, 6, 28]:

- overweight and obesity, especially visceral (BMI ≥ 25 kg / m²);
- burdened heredity (for example, the risk of CD-1 with a sibling disease - 4%, two siblings - 9.5%, a parent - 4-6%, a parent and sibling - 12%, both parents - 34%);
- race (Asian peoples, African Americans, Hispanics, Indians, residents of the

This can play the role of a predictor of future diabetes mellitus [30], and a dentist may for the first time establish a diagnosis of diabetes mellitus, since patients are poorly aware of the relationship between oral pathology and diabetes mellitus [13]. Patients with diabetes are not aware of the increased risk of developing dental diseases

Picture 1: Determination of blood glucose levels from the gingival crest with a portable glucometer

Features of dental treatment for patients with diabetes

Pedersen A.M.L., (2004) [30] developed recommendations for the organization of dental treatment of patients with diabetes: monitoring of glucose levels in a dental clinic (safe glucose level before invasive procedures - 5-6 mmol / l); appointment of patients in the morning, a few hours after the injection of insulin and breakfast; always have sugar in the office to relieve hypoglycemic attacks arising from waiting, anxiety, delay in eating, etc .; repeated visits of patients should be every 3 months, with high activity of dental diseases - more often.

On the one hand, dentoalveolar surgery, infections, stress from dental procedures can increase blood glucose levels and patients' metabolic insulin requirements. On the other hand, medications prescribed by dentists can influence diabetic therapy. For example, corticosteroids significantly impair glycemic control; a patient with type 2 diabetes may require short-term insulin therapy; antifungal drugs (miconazole, fluconazole) interfere with the metabolism of tolbutamide. Therefore, the treatment of patients with diabetes requires interaction between the dentist and the diabetologist [10, 30].

Thus, dental treatment of patients with diabetes should be carried out on the basis of a team approach, with the interaction of a dentist with an endocrinologist

(diabetologist) and other specialists. However, in order to carry out this interaction, both dentists and endocrinologists, and diabetic patients should have appropriate knowledge about the relationship between dental and diabetic pathology [34]. Meanwhile, the results of studies have shown that patients with diabetes have an insufficient level of knowledge about the relationship of their disease with dental health [10].

According to our data, 36% of patients in periodontal offices did not believe that diabetes affects dental health, 56% recognized the effect of diabetes on the state of the oral cavity, and only 8% realized that dental diseases can aggravate the course of diabetes. ... Every second patient (52%) did not understand that the state of the periodontium may depend on the level of blood glucose. Therefore, only 16% of periodontal patients regularly consulted a dentist, the rest - "from case to case" or

"If you have free time." Only 24% of patients assumed that they would definitely turn to an endocrinologist on the

referral of a dentist (16% - "would not apply", 60% - "if they had found free time"). However, dentists also did not have the necessary knowledge and underestimated the effect of periodontal disease on the course of diabetes, and 60% of doctors did not believe that tooth loss and abscesses are more frequent in patients with diabetes [35]. According to our data, the knowledge of dentists was limited, only 36% believed that dental pathology aggravated the course of diabetes. Only antibiotic therapy was named in the specifics of providing dental care to patients with diabetes.

The study of international and domestic practical recommendations for the management of patients with diabetes showed that they pay little attention to the relationship between diabetes and pathology of the oral cavity [1, 2, 4, 29]. Thus, the urgency of the problem of the relationship between diabetes mellitus and dental diseases, due to the high social significance, widespread prevalence and unfavorable interaction of pathologies, should be recognized.

Literature:

1. Dedov I.I. Diabetes mellitus is the most dangerous challenge to the world community // Bulletin of the severity of periodontitis in obese and / or type 2 diabetic chronic periodontitis patients // Quintessence RAMS. - 2012. - No. 1. - P.7-13.
2. Sabanov A.V., Gorbatkova I.V., Dyachenko T.S., Berdnik E.Yu. Territorial re-
3. Int. 2008. - Vol. 39, No. 6. - P. 485-489. history of diabetes mellitus in the Volgograd region for 2006-2010 // Volgograd scientific and tooth loss: a review of the literature // Compend Contin Educ Dent. - 2004. - Vol. 25, medical journal. - 2011. - No. 1. - S. 60-62.
4. IDF Diabetes Atlas. - 5th ed. - Update 2012. No. 3. - P. 179-184, 186-188, 190.
5. Petrov V.I., Rogova N.V., Mikhailova D.O. Pharmacoeconomic analysis of effective disease // Internet J Family Prac. - 2010. - Vol. 9, No. 1. - DOI: 10.5580 / 14c4. of complex therapy

- of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus // Bulletin of Volgograd State Medical University. 2010. - Issue. 1. - S. 28-32.
6. Borodina V.I., Zamyatina O.V., Povarova O.Yu., Sukhacheva A.P., Borodina M.A. Sugar-diseases: Sat. tr. 10th All-Russia. scientific-practical conf. - SPb: Man, 2013. -- S. 174-176. diabetes. Clinic, diagnostics, late complications, hypoglycemic and metabolic therapy // Teaching manual. - M.: MEDPRACTICA-M. - 2009. -- 60 p.
 7. Diabetes mellitus: diagnosis, treatment, prevention / ed. I.I. Dedova, M.V. Shestakova. - M.: Medical Information Agency, 2011. - S. 111-123.
 8. Saremi A., Nelson R. G., Tulloch-Reid M. et al. Periodontal disease and mortality in type 2 diabetes // Diabetes Care. - 2005. - Vol. 28. - P. 27-32.
 9. Southerland J.H., Moss K., Offenbacher S. Periodontitis and diabetes associations with measures of atherosclerosis and CHD // Atherosclerosis. - 2012. - Vol. 222, No. 1. - P. 196-201.
 10. Lal S., Cheng B., Kaplan S. et al. // Accelerated tooth eruption in children with diabetes mellitus // PEDIATRICS. - 2008. - Vol. 121, No. 5. - P. e1139-e1143.
 11. Ship J.A. Diabetes and oral health: an overview // JADA. 2003. Vol. 134, No. 4. - P. 1-10.
 12. Carda C., Mosquera-Lloreda N., Salom L. et al. Structural and functional salivary disorders in type 2 diabetic patients // Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal. - 2006. - Vol. 11, No. 4. - P. 309-314.
 13. Akpata E. S., Enosakhare S., Alomari Q. et al. Caries experience among children with type 1 diabetes in Kuwait // Pediatric Dentistry. - 2012. - Vol. 34, no. 7. - P. 468-472.
 14. Garton B.J., Ford P.J. Root caries and diabetes: risk assessment to improve oral and systemic health outcomes // Australian Dent J. - 2012. - Vol. 57, No. 2. - P. 114-122.
 15. Lopez-Lopez J., Jané-Salas E., Estrugo-Devesa A. et al. Periapical and endodontic status of type 2 diabetic patients in Catalonia, Spain: a cross-sectional study // J Endodont. - 2011. - Vol. 37, No. 5. - P. 598-601.
 16. Bakhshandeh S., Murtomaa H., Vehkalahti M.M. et al. Dental findings in diabetic adults // Car Res. - 2008. - Vol. 42, No. 1. - P. 14-18.
 17. Oates T. W., Huynh-Ba G., Vargas A. et al. A critical review of diabetes, glycemic control, and dental implant therapy // Clin Oral Implants Res. - 2013. - Vol. 24, No. 2. - P. 117-127.
 18. Casarin R.S., Barbagallo A. Meulman T. et al. Subgingival biodiversity in subjects with uncontrolled type-2 diabetes and chronic periodontitis // J Periodontal Res. - 2013. - Vol. 48, No. 1. - P. 30-36.
 19. Grossi S.G., Genco R.J. Periodontal disease and diabetes mellitus: a two-way relationship // Ann Periodontol. - 1998. - No. 3. - P. 51-61.
 20. Gursoy U.K., Marakoglu I., Oztop A.Y. Relationship between neutrophil functions and severity of periodontitis in obese and/or type 2 diabetic chronic periodontitis patients // Quintessence Int. 2008. — Vol. 39, № 6. — P. 485-489.
 20. Taylor G.W., Manz M.C., Borgnakke W.S. Diabetes, periodontal diseases, dental caries, and tooth loss: a review of the literature // Compend Contin Educ Dent. - 2004. - Vol. 25, No. 3. - P. 179-184, 186-188, 190.

21. Chandna S., Bathla M., Madaan V., Kalra S. Diabetes Mellitus - a risk factor for periodontal disease // *Internet J Family Prac.* - 2010. - Vol. 9, No. 1. - DOI: 10.5580 / 14c4.
22. Naumova V.N., Maslak E.E. The problem of diabetes in real dental practice tike (results of sociological research) // *Dentistry and socially significant diseases: Sat. tr. 10th All-Russia. scientific-practical conf.* - SPb: Man, 2013.-- S. 174-176.
23. Lalla E., Bin C., Shantanu L. et al. Periodontal changes in children and adolescents with diabetes: a case-control study // *Diabetes Care.* - 2006. - Vol. 29, No. 2. - P. 295-299.
24. Lopez R., Frydenberg M., Baelum V. Contextual effects in the occurrence of periodontal attachment loss and necrotizing gingival lesions among adolescents // *Eur J Oral Sci.* - 2009. - Vol. 117, No. 5. - P. 547-554.
25. Serrano C., Perez C., Rodriguez M. Periodontal conditions in a group of Colombian type 2 diabetic patients with different degrees of metabolic control // *Acta Odontol. Latinoam.* - 2012.Vol. 25, No. 1. - P. 130-137.
26. Alves C., Brandao M., Andion J., Menezes R. Oral health knowledge and habits in children with type 1 diabetes mellitus // *Braz Dent J.* - 2009. - Vol. 20, No. 41. - P. 70-73.
27. Merchant A. T., Oranbandid S., Mayer-Davis E. J. Oral care practices and A1c among youth with type 1 type 2 diabetes // *J Periodontol.* - 2012. - Vol. 83, No. 7. - P. 856-863.
28. Cinar A. B., Oktay I., Schou L. Self-efficacy perspective on oral health behaviour and diabetes management // *Oral Health Prev Dent.* . — 2012. — Vol. 10, № 4. — P. 379-387. American Diabetes Association. Diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus // *Diab. Care.* — 2011. — Vol. 34, Suppl. 1. — P. S62-S69.
29. Pedersen A.M.L. Diabetes mellitus and related oral manifestations // *Oral Biosci Med.* — 2004. — № 4. — P. 229-248.
30. Kaur G., Holtfreter B., Rathmann W. et al. Association between type 1 and type 2 diabetes with periodontal disease and tooth loss // *J Clin Periodontol.* — 2009. — Vol. 36, № 9. — P. 765-774.
31. Engstrom S., Berne C., Svardsudd K. Effectiveness of screening for diabetes mellitus in dental health care // *Diabet Med.* — 2013. — Vol. 30, № 2. — P. 239-245
32. Rosedale M.T., Strauss S.M. Diabetes screening at the periodontal visit: patient and provider experiences with two screening approaches // *Int J Dent Hyg.* —2012. — Vol. 10, № 4. — P. 250-258.
33. Koerber A., Peters K.E., Kaste L.M. et al. The views of dentists, nurses and nutritionists on the association between diabetes and periodontal disease: a qualitative study in a Latino community // *J Public Health Dent.* — 2006. — Vol. 66, № 3. — P. 212-215.
34. Al-Khabbaz A.K., Al-Shammari K.F. Diabetes Mellitus and periodontal health: dentists knowledge // *Med Princ Pract.* — 2011. — Vol. 20. — P. 538-544.